

Title	Problem statement <i>Articulate the main problem with the current situation.</i>	What could \$30k USD be used for <i>Initial ideas of what intervention at this scale could look like - we will continue to develop these in the discussion sessions.</i>	What are the arguments for funding this condition/cause <i>E.g. potential impact of additional investment/not investing, unmetness, readiness. Max 3 main bullet points.</i>
Preprint infrastructure	<p>Preprints provide rapid access to research outputs, more equitable participation in scholarship, and a valuable space for experimenting with how we share and review scholarly outputs.</p> <p>However, the preprints ecosystem is not yet financially sustainable and most preprints are not shared or reviewed using open infrastructure. Existing academic-led preprint services face significant risk from competition with for-profit, commercial, publisher-specific and other proprietary solutions.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning grant support for existing preprint services to investigate technical requirements and explore the feasibility of switching to existing open solutions • Convene a design workshop to generate new ideas for financing models to sustain open preprints services; and/or support the testing of these models without disrupting existing services • Hosting convenings/spaces to support preprint services/initiatives to improve equitable participation; and/or grants to community leads from under-served groups to start/run initiatives that support productive adoption of preprints 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We have many of the ingredients available today that are needed to support an ecosystem of preprint services run on open infrastructure. • Not investing in this would significantly increase the risk of for-profit players dominating the space and make it increasingly difficult for open services to be viable. • For-profits may also purchase flagship preprint servers such as bioRxiv and medRxiv, adding them to their commercial offerings rather than having them be community-governed. This would greatly limit the community's ability to continue to experiment with how open preprints might bring a much greater potential value.
Good community governance	<p>Effective and meaningful governance is a keystone to viable and sustainable open infrastructure. However, governance structures and processes are often seen as additional hurdles for organizations looking to simply get things done, and as “distractions”.</p> <p>Furthermore, there is no one right way to structure governance - organizations need capacity and knowledge to choose a suitable model depending on their specific internal factors and external environment.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grants to individual organizations to engage consultants and experts and/or convene committees/working groups with stakeholders, to evaluate existing governance and develop plans to further decentralize decision-making • Grants to individual organizations to be used for capacity building and resourcing for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Publicly disclosing governing procedures, annual reports and financial statements ◦ Establishing effective bi-directional channels to carry out meaningful conversations with stakeholders ◦ Subsidizing participation by individuals representing underrepresented/historical marginalized groups • Creating knowledge, e.g. a playbook and case studies on building a minimal viable system of community governance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the face of large commercial publishers looking to control the end-to-end infrastructures for the entire scholarly communication workflow and increasing marketization of research and scholarly infrastructure, governance that enables control by a broader range of community stakeholders is urgent and critical to ensure a wide array of voices are heard and broad interests are served by the infrastructures we depend on. • Additional investment in governance signals the importance of good governance to the broader infrastructure community, enabling organizations to prioritize governance needs as early as possible.
Financial health	<p>From our assessment of the financial health of 18 nonprofits in the research and scholarship sector, we found that many nonprofits in the space tend to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overly rely on a single type of revenue - Have insufficient cash on hand for contingencies - Have excessive liabilities relative to their available assets - Underinvest in human resources and other important operational expenses 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating resources and training materials, e.g. case studies and sample plans on how to reduce liabilities, manage costs, and increase revenue; guidebooks on fundraising • Hosting funder convenings to explore shared services to help manage common costs providing financial literacy and planning training to grantees • Capacity building grants to support: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Financial planning, e.g. revenue strategy, liability reduction, operational reserves, through accessing financial consultants/advisor 	<p>Not funding this will mean:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increasing the open infrastructure ecosystem's vulnerability to external financial fluctuations • Limiting the ability to build up critical operating reserves • Preventing the development of a robust and sustainable ecosystem of open services for research

	This increases their vulnerability to external financial fluctuations, limits their ability to build up critical operating reserves, and can be problematic for the long-term sustainability of these organizations providing enduring services over the long term.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Fundraising and portfolio diversification efforts through accessing fundraising consultant/planning services 	
Critical and at-risk infrastructure	<p>Infrastructure often can go unnoticed until there's a disruption in service. In recent years, we've seen both for- and non-profit infrastructure offerings that are heavily relied on in the research and scholarly ecosystem struggle to maintain stable funding, use, and in many cases, get purchased by for-profit entities.</p> <p>This poses an ongoing risk that infrastructure services heavily utilized by the research and scholarly community will be sold to the highest bidder or shutter due to lack of funding.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Bridge funding for open infrastructure services in need of continuation support when funding is disrupted. ● Emergency funds for unplanned contingencies that present an existential threat to the organization ● Funds for legal expertise to develop organizational structures to help nonprofit organizations thrive despite threats from for-profit, commercial providers ● Hosted convenings to discuss a "community buyback" strategy for countering offers from for-profit entities to buy and enclose infrastructure that serves research and scholarship 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Not funding this would continue to expose the research ecosystem to increased commoditization and enclosure by extractive, for-profit entities. ● Funding in this area would ensure a viable financial safety net for organizations that ensure providers are supported through unforeseen contingencies. ● Funding in this area would protect nonprofit entities from being consolidated under the control of for-profit entities or otherwise removed from community control and public accountability.
Technical reliability and security	<p>Open source provides vast flexibility for developers and engineers to build on each other's work and innovate faster in response to community's needs. This creates an ecosystem of open technologies that are mutually dependent on each other.</p> <p>However, many open source projects suffer from perpetual underinvestment into maintaining infrastructure and community development and maintenance, and accumulating technical debt. This leads to increased vulnerability across the open-source ecosystem.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Capacity building grants to individual open infrastructure services to develop greater awareness of any latent risk in their technical and human infrastructure, and develop successful mitigation strategies to counter these identified risks ● Development of a risk monitoring system assessing dependencies, health, and other issues to guide decision making and resource allocation ● Financial support to manage labor and ongoing maintenance costs 	<p>Not funding this will mean:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Open infrastructure services continue to stretch their core maintainer base and developers to the limit and to accumulate technical debt ● Open infrastructure services are unable to scale beyond a small, limited set of users and functionality ● Open infrastructure services continue to be vulnerable to various threats (data theft, denial of service, ransomware, etc.) and put their users at high risk for theft, fraud, and abuse
Adoption	<p>To make open infrastructure the default in research, we need to raise awareness for open infrastructure services and build capacity around their use to ultimately increase their adoption.</p> <p>From our conversations and research, we have heard that decision makers and users often find it challenging to discover open infrastructure services. They also struggle to choose to adopt a fledging open service as opposed to an established, reputable, commercial service.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Grants to individual open infrastructure services to develop <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Marketing plans and materials to raise awareness for their services ○ Training materials and programmes for users to ease adoption ● Grants to support local initiatives to develop community engagement and training programmes to increase the adoption of open infrastructure in their communities ● Capacity building grants for institutions to explore, adopt, and contribute to open alternatives for a commercial service they current use, and to assess migration needs to move away from the commercial service 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Investment in this area will set up more open services to become more obvious (if not the default) choices for institutions and scholars. ● Investment in this area will grow the user base for open infrastructure services, particularly among early career researchers and has the potential to fundamentally alter how science is done as researchers shift away from proprietary to open source tools as the default in their work. ● Not investing here will significantly increase the risk for further acquisitions of open services by commercial, for-profit players, increasing their end-to-end control across the research workflow.